

Efficient Low-Cost Time Domain Calibration and Validation of Aerospace LISNs

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Abstract—Conducted emissions measurements are a must in the aerospace industry to ensure the intended electromagnetic performance of on-board systems. Line Impedance Stabilization Networks are a key element for such tests since they provide a stable and reliable reference impedance. However, the LISN response can degrade over time due to typical wear, environmental factors, vibrations, or aging, potentially compromising the measurement accuracy. Regular calibration is, therefore, critical to maintain measurement integrity. Traditional LISN calibrations involve costly and complex equipment, such as vector network analyzers and impedance meters. This paper proposes an alternative and cost-effective method for LISN calibration using general-purpose oscilloscopes and arbitrary waveform generators to determine the voltage division factor and input impedance. The approach is validated by calibrating a custom LISN built according to ECSS standards. This method reduces costs, simplifies the calibration process, and allows users to perform, in-house, internal verifications.

Index Terms—arbitrary waveform generator, calibration, LISN, oscilloscope, time-domain measurements

I. INTRODUCTION

In the aerospace industry, accurate electromagnetic emissions measurements are critical to ensure the safety and reliability of on-board systems. The most frequent EMC tests performed to assess electromagnetic disturbances are those evaluating the conducted emissions. In this regard, Line Impedance Stabilization Networks (LISNs) are employed to fix a stable and standardized impedance in the power supply port of the equipment under test. This is needed for repeatable and reproducible test outcomes. In consequence, the accuracy of such measurements is highly dependent on the proper functioning and calibration of the LISNs.

This work was supported in part by the project 21NRM06 EMC-STD which has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, cofinanced from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States, and in part by the "Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación" of Spain through the Project DIN2021-012003 under Grant MCIN/AEI/10.13039/50110001103.

Periodic calibrations and verifications of the LISN are good laboratory practices and are recommended to assure the quality and integrity of the test results. Over time, components within the LISN might degrade due to environmental factors, vibrations, or aging [1]. These changes can lead to shifts in LISN characteristics, potentially resulting in erroneous measurements and invalid test conclusions. Furthermore, this is even more important in the aerospace industry, where minor deviations from emissions measurements can have significant implications [2], [3]. Regular verification and calibration of LISNs provide higher confidence that they continue to operate within the required specifications and that test results are accurate and repeatable.

Traditionally, such calibrations are carried out using specialized and expensive equipment, such as vector network analyzers (VNAs) and impedance meters. Although they provide very accurate results, they increase the cost and complexity of the calibrations.

This work proposes an alternative approach to conduct LISN calibrations, specifically to obtain the voltage division factor (VDF) and input impedance using general-purpose signal generators and oscilloscopes. This method is intended to become a fast, effective, less expensive alternative to traditional calibrations. In addition, by using general-purpose elements, end users will have more options to perform the said verifications and calibrations with their readily available instrumentation and avoid relying on external services.

In this study, we used a homemade LISN according to ECSS [4] as a test subject. The details of the manufactured LISN, as well as of the proposed calibration procedure, are given below. Values of VDF and impedance are obtained for this LISN. The results are compared with the ideal LISN response obtained from circuit simulation and validated using independent VNA measurements.

II. STUDY CASE

As mentioned, the homemade LISN is built according to the model and specifications proposed in ECSS-E-ST-20-07C [5]. Specifications include an operating frequency range from 9 kHz - 100 MHz and two port capability, for the positive and negative lines. Additionally, and beyond the standard model, it was considered to integrate an RF measurement port in order to provide the possibility of measuring disturbance voltage as part of the conducted emissions test. This port should be terminated with 50Ω when conducting the measurements. Schematic of such LISN is depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. LISN schematic.

The system is built into a 17 cm x 12 cm x 5.5 cm metal enclosure as shown in Fig 2. All components are chosen to be able to support DC voltages up to 100 V and currents of 6 A. Inductors are wound using a low-permeability 3D-printed core. Each inductor consists of 11 turns with a diameter of 35 mm and a total coil length of 72 mm. Finally, to avoid magnetic coupling between inductors, a grounded metallic shield is placed between them.

Fig. 2. Upper view of manufactured LISN.

The prototype is equipped with banana plugs to connect to the EUT and the power supply. Two BNC connectors are additionally integrated on the EUT side. The front face can be observed in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Front view of homemade manufactured LISN.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Multitone generation

The excitation consists of a multitone signal formed by 37 different frequencies with the same amplitude. It is important to assemble this multitone by reducing its crest factor, avoiding spectral leakage, and preventing dynamic range compression. The chosen algorithm is the method proposed by Schroeder [6]–[8]. The phase of each tone is defined according to the following equation:

$$\phi_k = \phi_1 - 2\pi \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} (k-i)p_i, \quad (1)$$

for $k = (2, 3, \dots, K)$. ϕ_k represents the phase of each sinus component in the multitone, p_i is the relative power of i -th component, and K denotes the number of tones. If all the components are meant to be the same amplitude ($p_1 = p_2 = \dots = p_K$), equation (1) can be simplified as:

$$\phi_k = \phi_1 - \frac{k(k-1)}{K}\pi. \quad (2)$$

The generated signal is intended to cover the frequency range from 10 kHz to 100 MHz. In each decade, 10 linearly spaced tones are generated. For example, tones separated 10 kHz in the range from 10 kHz to 100 kHz, tones separated 100 kHz in the range from 100 kHz to 1 MHz, etc... Spectrum of the generated signal can be observed in Fig. 4. The employed resolution bandwidth for all the experiments and measurements is 1 kHz.

The amplitude decay in tones above 20 MHz is observed due to band-limiting effects. Nonetheless, by conducting a normalization measure, it is intended to correct this effect.

B. Voltage division factor

The VDF is defined as the relation as a function of the frequency between the voltage level at the EUT power connector and the output of the RF connector. As the used LISN has two ports (positive and negative), it is necessary to determine the VDF for each.

Fig. 4. Spectrum of the generated multitone signal.

A two-step process must be followed for the VDF measurement. The first one is to normalize path losses using the setup in Fig. 5, and posteriorly, change the setup and conduct the calibration as shown in Fig. 6. Such configurations are based on a similar procedure described in CISPR 16-1-2 [9].

Fig. 5. Voltage division factor normalization setup.

Fig. 6. Voltage division factor measurement setup.

The measurement receiver operates in the time-domain (TD), and it is formed by a low-cost general-purpose oscilloscope (Picoscope 5444D) in combination with the software emiGO by EMC Barcelona, which computes the spectrum of the acquired signal according to CISPR 16-1-1. Photos of normalization and measurement set-up employing the former system can be observed in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, respectively.

In this case, a banana-to-BNC adapter was used to connect the coaxial cables to the input EUT port of the LISN. To

Fig. 7. VDF normalization set-up employing the proposed method.

Fig. 8. VDF measurement set-up employing the proposed method.

obtain VDF, the logarithmic peak magnitude of the multitone obtained in the normalization setup is subtracted from the spectrum obtained in the calibration setup.

The obtained results are compared with equivalent measurements employing a VNA. When employing VNA, instrument calibration should be conducted using a normalization adjustment (Fig. 5) and then measure the scattering parameter S_{21} .

Photos of normalization and measurement setup employing a VNA are shown in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, respectively.

It is important to remark that for the VNA used, the minimum measurable frequency is 300 kHz. Finally, results are compared to the ones obtained by circuit simulation run on LTspice.

C. Impedance

The input impedance measurement is an essential characteristic defined by the standard and provided for each single LISN circuit. Two main types of impedance are specified: the differential impedance between positive and negative EUT ports and the impedance between each port and common ground. In this study, for the sake of simplicity, only the impedance of each port relative to ground will be evaluated.

To conduct the impedance measurement, the normalization setup will be used (Fig. 5 and Fig. 7). However, in this

Fig. 9. VDF measurement setup employing a VNA.

Fig. 10. VDF normalization setup employing a VNA.

experiment, an RF current probe (Solar 9123-1N) is placed on the live wire of the banana plug-to-BNC adaptor. Set-up for conducting the impedance measurement is shown in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Impedance measurement using a current probe.

Using the oscilloscope, a synchronized measurement is made between the current flowing through the live and the

voltage measured at the BNC T-adaptor. Using logarithmic units of voltage and current ($\text{dB}\mu\text{V}$ and $\text{dB}\mu\text{A}$), the impedance in decibel-ohm can be calculated simply by subtracting the two values. When employing the VNA, port 1 is connected directly to the BNC adaptor, and impedance can be derived straightforwardly from S_{11} .

IV. RESULTS

In this section, experimental results employing the proposed method in time-domain (blue traces), results obtained by means of the VNA (orange traces), and simulations (green traces) are compared for positive and negative ports.

A. Voltage division factor

Voltage division factor obtained at positive and negative port with respect to ground is shown in Fig. 12 and Fig. 13, respectively.

Fig. 12. VDF for positive port.

Fig. 13. VDF for negative port.

For frequencies up to 50 MHz, experimental measurements employing the VNA and the proposed method coincide for

both channels. The proposed method shows slight resonance and divergences above 50 MHz. One reason can be the effect of employing the banana-BNC adapter, which was sensitive to changing the position for frequencies above 30 MHz. Up to 10 MHz, the proposed method and simulation match excellently, except for the tone at 10 kHz, an observation that remains to be double-checked.

B. Impedance

Impedance obtained at positive and negative port respect to ground is shown in Fig. 14 and Fig. 15 respectively.

Fig. 14. Impedance of positive port.

Fig. 15. Impedance of negative port.

For impedance values above 1Ω , measurement employing the proposed method show exact results with simulation up to 25 MHz. When assessing values below 1Ω , which are found on the lower frequency range, results diverge between the proposed method and simulation. Above 25 MHz, VNA and the proposed method measures show similar behavior, although they exhibit a higher impedance due to the influence of the BNC adapter itself. It is noteworthy that between 300 kHz and 25 MHz, simulation results are closer to the proposed method rather than the measures taken with the VNA.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A fast and effective method for the verification of LISNs is proposed. This method uses general-purpose oscilloscopes and function generators, instruments that most laboratories usually count with. The approach is applied on a homemade and custom LISN inspired by the circuit proposed in the ECSS-E-ST-20-07C Rev.2. For such LISN, values of VDF and impedance are extracted and compared with the values obtained using both VNA measurements and circuit simulation.

The test results and simulations match excellently in the range from 40 kHz up to 10 MHz. There are divergences between measurements and simulation for lower frequencies due to non-idealities and parasitic effects found in practice and not modeled in the circuit. In fact, the banana-to-BNC adapter effect is not considered in the model, and it is of influence in the highest range considered, thus compromising the comparisons with the simulation.

Regarding LISN assembly, part of the deviations observed could be explained by parasitic effects, mainly the capacitance between windings of the core inductor, the capacitance from elements to the metallic chassis, or the non-ideality of the cables used to connect the internal components. Compared to earlier prototypes (not reported in this work), such parasitic effects were reduced by improving the LISN circuit geometry and disposition of components. Still, independently of the root cause of the deviations observed with respect to the ideal LISN response for frequencies above 10 MHz, it is noticeable that there is a very good agreement between the measurements obtained with the proposed method and those from the VNA.

The factors obtained with calibration methods such as the one proposed in this paper can be compared with those provided by the manufacturer at the time of purchase in order to verify whether the equipment can continue to be used as before or whether correction factors have to be modified significantly, or in the most extreme case even determine that a certain instrument can no longer be used due to severe changes in calibration factors. For this reason, regular verification of measuring instruments can greatly help assess whether a piece of equipment has become out of tolerance and is not appropriate for further use.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We want to recognize the kind help and support from the EMC area from Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial “Esteban Terradas” (INTA), Torrejón de Ardoz, Spain, for their advice in the LISN manufacturing process and lending us a reference LISN according to the MIL-STD-461 to carry out preliminary checks as part of this study.

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